

Reward and Fictive Prediction Error signals in ventral striatum: asymmetry between factual and counterfactual processing

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ABSTRACT

Reward prediction error, the difference between the expected and obtained reward, is known to act as a reinforcement learning neural signal. In the current study, we propose a model fitting approach that combines behavioural and neural data to fit computational models of reinforcement learning. Briefly, we penalized subject-specific fitted parameters that moved away too far from the group median, except when that deviation led to an improvement in the model's fit to neural responses. By means of a probabilistic monetary learning task and fMRI, we compared our approach with standard model fitting methods. Q-learning outperformed actor-critic at both behavioral and neural level, although the inclusion of neuroimaging data into model fitting improved the fit of actorcritic models. We observed both action-value and state-value prediction error signals in the striatum, while standard model fitting approaches failed to capture state-value signals. Finally, left ventral striatum correlated with reward prediction error while right ventral striatum with fictive prediction error, suggesting a functional hemispheric asymmetry regarding prediction-error driven learning.

INTRODUCTION

Model-based fMRI analysis has been widely used to study the neural correlates of learning (Gläscher and O’Doherty 2010), particularly prediction error signals (Schultz 2016; O’Doherty et al. 2017). Computational models are usually fitted to behavioral data, optimizing model parameters to maximize similarity between model predictions and actual behaviour. Then, fMRI regressors are created either averaging model parameters across subjects or using individual parameter estimates (Chase et al. 2015). Group average parameters usually provides more robust multisubject fMRI results (Daw 2011), but individual parameter estimates can account for the individual differences in behaviour (Estes and Maddox 2005) and neural responses (Cohen 2007). However, although an optimal parameter estimation can provide a good description of behaviour, it does not necessarily imply a correspondence to the computations performed by different brain regions (Wilson and Niv 2015). Indeed, multiple learning systems can coexist in a particular brain region (Colas et al. 2017), different brain regions can have different learning rates (Gläscher and Büchel 2005; Bornstein and Daw 2012) or even fit to different learning models (Gläscher et al. 2010; Wan Lee et al. 2014).

In the current study, we proposed a method for combining behavioural and neural data in model fitting. Particularly, we fitted models to behavioural data, preventing individual model parameters to move away from the group median unless this deviation led to an improvement in model fit to neural responses. Several approaches have been proposed for the combination of behavioural and neural data (Turner et al. 2017). Among these we can mention modelling both neural and behavioural data simultaneously (Turner et al. 2013), predicting neural data with behavioural models (O’Doherty et al. 2007; Gläscher and O’Doherty 2010) and constraining behavioural models with neural data (Purcell et al. 2010). The model fitting approach presented here belongs to the second category but also shares elements with the third, since model parameters were constrained using neural data.

In order to assess this approach, we used a probabilistic reinforcement learning task and functional MRI data in a sample of healthy subjects. We compared the goodness of fit of two families of models: Q-learning (Watkins and Dayan 1992) and actor-critic (Barto 1995). The former is thought to better capture learning based on the representation of reward values of competing actions in the prefrontal cortex (Gold 2012), while the latter is thought to better capture stimulus-response associations in the basal ganglia (Montague et al. 1996; O’Doherty et al. 2004). Furthermore, we extended these models to include fictive prediction error, i.e., the difference between predicted and missed outcome of non-selected actions, since counterfactual processing can influence learning (Hoeck et al. 2015; Byrne 2016) and fictive learning signals have been found in ventral striatum (Lohrenz et al. 2007; Büchel et al. 2011) and prefrontal regions (Daw et al. 2011; Deserno et al. 2015). While a whole-brain voxel-wise analysis would have been adequate to localize which brain regions fit to each model, here we were not interested in localizing but, instead, in comparing the fit to different models in brain regions known to be involved in the processing of reward. For this reason, we conducted these analyses in the following regions of interest: ventral and dorsal striatum, orbitofrontal cortex, ventromedial prefrontal cortex, presupplementary motor area, anterior insula and dorsal anterior cingulate cortex (Chase et al. 2015; O’Doherty et al. 2017), and performed multivariate regression analyses to select the best models and variables for each brain region.

METHODS

Participants

We invited right-handed, healthy adults to participate in the study through advertisements in the community, social networks and word of mouth. Of the 35 initially recruited individuals, we excluded one because of a potential psychiatric disorder, one because his/her MRI showed incidental findings, one due to excessive head movement during the MRI acquisition, and two because they did not learn during the task. Therefore, the final sample included 30 subjects. For a detailed information about exclusion criteria see Supplementary Material. All participants gave written informed consent prior to participation. The Research Ethics Committee of FIDMAG had previously approved all study procedures, which adhered to the Declaration of Helsinki. Participants received a gift-card as a compensation for their participation in the study.

Data acquisition

During the fMRI-scan, subjects performed a probabilistic reinforcement learning task (adapted from Pessiglione *et al.*, 2006) (Figure 1). In each trial, subjects had to select one of the two stimuli presented in the screen, after which a coin of 10-cents (gain) or a yellow circle (no gain) was displayed. To maximize earnings, subjects had to learn, by essay and error, which stimulus was most rewarded for each pair of stimuli. Ten different pairs of stimuli were shown sequentially during 16 trials each. Probabilistic stimulus-outcome contingencies were used. In half of pairs of stimuli, the probabilities of reward for each stimulus were 80:20% (reward condition), while in the other half were 50:50% (bivalent condition). For a detailed information about experimental task, see Supplementary Material.

All neuroimaging analysis were performed using the signal extracted from regions-of-interest. In a theory-driven approach, we selected those brain regions known for their role in reward learning: ventral and dorsal striatum, orbitofrontal cortex, ventromedial prefrontal cortex, pre-supplementary motor area, anterior insula and dorsal anterior cingulate cortex. Images were preprocessed using FEAT module included in the FSL (FMRIB Software Library) software (Smith *et al.* 2004). Behavioural analysis, computational modelling and statistical analysis were performed in R 3.4.4 (R Core Team 2014). For a detailed information about image acquisition, preprocessing and ROI coordinates, see Supplementary Material.

Computational models

We implemented six computational models of reinforcement learning: the standard Q-learning, referred as QL1 in the text (Watkins and Dayan 1992), and actor-critic, referred as AC1 (Barto 1995; Joel *et al.* 2002), two extended models for Q-learning (referred as QL2 and QL3), and two for actor-critic (referred as AC2 and AC3). In all models, the expected value of the chosen action is updated trial-by-trial based on reward prediction error, and in the extended models, the expected value of the unchosen action is updated trial-by-trial based on fictive prediction error. The influence of prediction errors on updating forward predictions are weighted by the same rate of learning (α) for reward and fictive prediction error in one version of the extended models (QL2 and AC2 models), while in the other version different rates of learning are estimated for factual and counterfactual information (QL3 and AC3 models). For a detailed information about the models, see Supplementary Material.

Standard model fitting

Models were fitted to behavioural data using the maximum likelihood technique at individual level. To compare the fit of different models, we performed a random-effects Bayesian Model Selection (Stephan *et al.* 2009; Rigoux *et al.* 2014), implemented by VBA toolbox (Daunizeau *et al.* 2014). As input for the random-effects BMS we used the (negative) Akaike's information criterion (AIC) and the (negative) Bayesian information criterion (BIC) as approximations of the log model evidence (Penny *et al.* 2004; Stephan *et al.* 2009). AIC and BIC were calculated using the sum of the log likelihood of the fitted models at individual level, and the sign of both was inverted (multiplying by -1) so that higher values indicated greater evidence. At group level, we reported the exceedance probability (probability of any given model to be more frequent than all other models) and the estimated model frequency. At individual level, we reported the best model for each subject, i.e., posterior probability as model attribution per subject.

Combined fitting using neuroimaging data

In addition to the standard model fitting, we also fitted the models to both behavioural and neuroimaging data using the following procedure, so-called 'combined fitting' from now on. A schematic description of methods is shown in Figure 2, pseudocode is shown in Figure S1 in Supplementary Material and code is available in <https://github.com/asantoangles/rpe>. We added a penalization parameter λ to the individual model fitting to avoid each free parameter in a subject to be too different from the median of the sample.

For example, in a model with a single free parameter (α), the sum of log likelihoods ($p_{c,i}$) of the observed responses of each individual would be as follows, where α_{median} is the median α of the sample and λ_α is the penalizing parameter for α . Given that we tested models with more than one free parameter, we penalized each of them separately. We estimated the optimal value of the penalization parameter maximizing the similarity between the empirical BOLD signal in each ROI and the fMRI regressors derived from computational models (expected BOLD signal). To avoid the circularity problem of using the same data for parameter estimation and statistical inference, we estimated the penalization parameter using the cross-validation approach.

For each fold of the cross-validation, we divided the sample in test ($n=3$) and train ($n=27$) subsamples. In the train subsample, we calculated the median of each free parameter (rate of learning and inverse temperature) from the individual fitted parameters using maximum likelihood estimation. Then, we fitted the computational model, e.g., Q-learning, including the penalization term in the likelihood function with different values of the penalization parameter λ (five values from 0.2 to 1 in segments of 0.2). We generated the time-series of the hidden variables of the model, e.g. reward prediction error (see a detailed description of hidden variables per model in Supplementary Material), and we convolved them to get the fMRI regressors and their temporal derivatives (expected BOLD signal) using FSL FEAT (Woolrich et al. 2001). For each value of the penalization parameter, we fitted a linear regression model with the empirical BOLD signal as a response variable and the expected BOLD signal in addition to its temporal derivative as predictor variables. Then, we fitted a metaanalytic random-effects model (restricted maximum-likelihood estimator or REML method in the `rma` function of `metafor` R package) with the individual regression coefficients and their variances, getting a measure of fit between empirical and expected BOLD signal (z-value) for each value of the penalization parameter. We selected the penalizing parameter that provided the highest fit to BOLD signal in the train sample. Then, in the test sample, we fitted the models with the selected penalization parameter, and assessed the association between expected and empirical BOLD signal with the same procedure. We repeated this procedure 10 times to achieve that all subjects were included only once in the test sample, getting a measure of group fit between each variable of the computational models and BOLD signal for each ROI, thus avoiding overfitting or circularity issues. Note that we applied the described procedure for each region-of-interest and each hidden variable of each model.

In addition, we applied the same procedure, e.g., linear regression at individual level and meta-analytic random-effect at group level, to analyse the association between the BOLD signal and the appearance of the following events of the task: presentation of stimuli, response onset and feedback delivery (winning, non-winning, or both combined). As we performed a total of 562 univariate regression analysis per model fitting strategy, we familywise-corrected for multiple comparisons using the 'Holm' method (Holm 1970). Corrected p-values below 0.05 were considered significant.

Neuroimaging multivariate analysis

With univariate results for each ROI, we selected the variable(s) and model(s) that most adjusted to the BOLD signal using the following algorithm (pseudocode is shown in Figure S2 in Supplementary Material). First, we discarded any variable that did not achieve the significance level of the Holm correction in the univariate analysis. Second, we selected the variable with the largest statistical significance and conducted a set of multiple regressions that included the selected variable and one of the remaining variables. When these two variables were collinear (variance inflation factor ≥ 2) in at least half of participants, we considered that we were not able to rule out which variable we should select, and thus conducted the process twice, one for each variable. When one of the variables lost the Holm statistical significance, we discarded it. If the selected variable kept the statistical significance in all regressions, we selected the variable with the largest statistical significance in the multiple regression from the latter group and conducted a set of multiple regressions that included the two selected variables and one of the remaining variables. With this approach, for each ROI, we end up with one (or more) multivariate regression model(s) with the variable(s) that most adjusted to the BOLD signal. Note that more than one multivariate regression model could be significant for each ROI because of the multicollinearity between variables, normally because of the multicollinearity of the same variable from different models, e.g., RPE from QL1 and

QL3. In this case, we used the BIC from the meta-analytic random-effects to select the best model(s) in terms of fit to BOLD signal. According to (Kass and Raftery 1995): models with a difference in BIC equal or less than 2 were considered indistinguishable, and the evidence against the model with highest BIC was considered positive with difference between 2 and 6, strong between 6 and 10, and very strong above 10. To select the best model(s) in a ROI with several collinear signals from different models, we adopted a more conservative strategy, e.g., discarding only those models whose difference in BIC with the best model was greater than 10. Note that BIC used in this section (obtained from meta-analytic random-effects) was not the same as BIC used in random-effects Bayesian Model Selection. The former was based on the fit to neural data, and the latter was based on the fit to behavioral data.

Comparison among model fitting methods

To assess whether the inclusion of neuroimaging into model fitting improved the prediction of neural data, we also created fMRI regressors with models fitted to behavioural data (standard model fitting). We generated fMRI regressors using the individual estimates of free parameters ('individual fitting') and their group median ('fixed group fitting'). Then, we applied the same statistical approach and multiple comparisons correction to test the association between expected and empirical BOLD signal, i.e., individual linear regression and group meta-analytic random-effects model, achieving a comparable measure of fit among model fitting procedures. To assess whether 'combined fitting' improved the prediction of behaviour, we created surrogate data (600 simulations) for each model and fitting approach, and plotted the actual and simulated learning curves, i.e., model predictions for reward condition (trials with 80:20 reward contingencies). Moreover, to assess parameter recovery, we fitted the models with surrogate data and correlated the true parameters from actual data with recovered parameters from surrogate data (Wilson and Collins 2019).

Laterality index

To quantify the hemispheric asymmetry reported in ventral striatum (see results below), we computed the lateralization index (Seghier 2008)

$$LI = f \frac{Q_{LH} - Q_{RH}}{|Q_{LH}| + |Q_{RH}|}$$

where Q_{LH} and Q_{RH} were the individual measures of prediction error fit to BOLD signal, i.e., z-score of regression coefficient. The scaling factor f was held to 1, making LI vary from -1 (right hemisphere) to 1 (left hemisphere), being the usual threshold value for hemispheric dominance $|LI| > 0.2$. To test the hypothesis of hemispheric asymmetry in ventral striatum, we compared lateralization indices for reward and fictive prediction error signals with a paired samples Wilcoxon test.

Whole-brain analysis

In order to assess that ventral striatum results were not guided by ROIs position, we performed an exploratory wholebrain analysis. ROI-based significant results of ventral striatum, i.e., reward prediction error of QL1 in left VS and negative fictive prediction error of QL3 in right VS, were introduced as modulated regressors of interest. We also included outcome delivery as nuisance regressor. For a detailed description of whole-brain preprocessing and analysis, see Supplementary Material.

RESULTS

The sample included 30 subjects (14 males 16 females; mean age 34.3 years, SD=13.5; mean IQ 104.0, SD=12.1). In reward condition, the proportion of optimal choices in the last half of trials (0.87 ± 0.11) was similar to the reward contingencies of the most rewarded stimulus (80%), indicating a good learning (Figure 3). The amount of money the subjects earned was $9.12\text{€} \pm 0.46\text{€}$.

Standard model fitting

Parameter estimates are shown in Table 1 (see the distribution of parameters in Figures S3-4 in Supplementary Material). Random-effects Bayesian Model Selection (RFX) showed that Q-learning models overcame actor-critic (estimated frequency for QL family = 0.94 [RFX-AIC] and 0.98 [RFX-BIC]; exceedance probability = 1 [RFX-AIC, RFX-BIC]). Note that we reported RFX results obtained using both AIC and BIC (Table 3) as approximations to the log model evidence. Among Q-learning models, the best model was QL1 (estimated frequency = 0.43 [RFX-AIC], 0.60 [RFX-BIC]; exceedance probability = 0.79 [RFX-AIC], 0.90 [RFX-BIC]), followed by QL2 (estimated frequency = 0.30 [RFX-AIC], 0.38 [RFX-BIC]; exceedance probability = 0.17 [RFX-AIC], 0.10 [RFX-BIC]). Subject-specific model attributions showed that behaviour of some subjects was better explained by extended Q-learning models (QL2 and QL3), and one subject showed AC3 as the best model (Figure 4E-F). Simulated data from standard model fitting showed that all Q-learning models resembled the actual learning curves of subjects, but Actor-Critic models did not. Only AC3 partially approached the actual behaviour, but AC1 was below and AC2 was above the current learning curve (Figure 4A). Finally, parameter recovery showed that surrogate data generated from Q-learning models successfully recovered parameter estimates from empirical data, overcoming actor-critic models (Figure S9 in Supplementary Material).

Combined fitting

Parameter estimates of combined fitting are shown in Table 2 (see the distribution of parameters in Figures S5-6 and the distribution of penalization term in Figures S7-8 in Supplementary Material). Combined fitting improved the predictions of standard actor-critic model (AC1), but the extended models (AC2 and AC3) overestimated the actual performance (Figure 4B-D). Predictions from Q-learning were not improved with combined fitting. Note that we did not show the predictions of behaviour of models fitted to all ROIs, since results did not differ qualitatively from the ROIs presented in Figure 4 (left VS and bilateral DS).

Neuroimaging results for ‘combined fitting’

In figures 5 and 6, we displayed which model variables showed a significant fit to the BOLD signal within each ROI. All variables reported were significant in univariate regression analysis after correction for multiple comparisons, and survived to the multivariate regression analysis described above. We indicated those cases where multicollinearity between variables prevented them from being included in the same multiple regression model. When signals derived from different models were collinear, we reported the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) from meta-analytic random-effects to discriminate among models. For detailed information about results, see the list of multivariate regression models per ROI in Table S1 and the list of significant univariate results in Table S2 in Supplementary Material.

Ventral striatum (VS)

Left VS activity was associated with delivery of feedback ($z=5.34$, $p=2e-5$) and reward prediction error from models QL1, QL3, AC2 and AC3 (range across models, $z=[4.3, 4.8]$, $p=[1e-5, 2e-6]$) (Figure 5A). Although multicollinearity prevented differentiating prediction error signals among models, BIC from meta-analytic random-effects model showed that RPE from QL1 (BIC = 277.24) and AC3 (BIC = 277.94) showed a positive evidence of better fit to BOLD signal than RPE from AC2 (BIC = 280.25) and QL3 (BIC = 280.38) (Figure 5B).

Right VS showed a positive association with the delivery of feedback ($z=5.7$, $p=1e-8$) and with negative fictive prediction error (FPE) of QL3 ($z=5.7$, $p=1e-8$) (Figure 5C). Note that we inverted the sign of negative prediction error signals in regression analysis to facilitate interpretation. A positive association with negative FPE means that the higher the (absolute) value of fictive prediction error, the higher the bold signal.

Dorsal Striatum (DS)

Left DS activity showed a significant association with delivery of feedback ($z=7.3$, $p=2e-5$) and reward prediction error from QL1, QL3, AC2 and AC3 models ($z=[5.36, 5.78]$, $p=[7e-6, 7e-7]$) (Figure 5E). Multicollinearity prevented differentiation among models, and BIC from meta-analytic random-effects model showed that RPE signal from AC3 showed positive evidence of better fit to BOLD signal (AC3: BIC = 273.03; QL1: BIC = 276.36; AC2: BIC = 278.56; QL3 = 279.36) (Figure 5F). In addition, multivariate model with RPE of AC2 and feedback delivery also showed a significant expected value signal from QL2 model ($z=-3.96$, $p=6e-3$). Right DS showed a positive association with the delivery of feedback ($z=4.02$, $p=5e-3$) and a negative association with expected value from models QL1, QL3, AC2 and AC3 ($z=[-7.55, -6.6]$, $p=[1e-10, 4e-9]$) (Figure 5G), although multicollinearity prevented differentiate among models. BIC from meta-analytic random-effects showed that expected value from model QL1 showed strong evidence of better fit (QL1: BIC = 262.41; AC2: BIC = 269.36; AC3: BIC = 271; QL3: BIC = 272.67) (Figure 5H). Moreover, right DS showed a positive association with RPE of QL1, QL3, AC2 and AC3 models ($z=[4.87, 6.56]$, $p=[9e-5, 5e-9]$) (Figure 5G). All these signals showed multicollinearity, but BIC from metaanalytic random-effects showed that RPE signals from QL1 (BIC = 272.23) showed positive evidence of better fit to BOLD signal than AC3 (BIC = 276.06) and strong evidence than the remaining models (AC2: BIC = 278.3; QL3: BIC = 278.31) (Figure 5D).

Anterior insula

Left anterior insula showed a positive association with delivery of feedback ($z=7.9$, $p=3e-15$), a negative association with the expected value estimated by QL1 ($z=[-6.7, -5.3]$, $p=[2e-10, 1e-7]$), and a positive association with negative FPE of QL3 ($z=6.3$, $p=2e-10$), the higher the (absolute) value of fictive prediction error, the higher the BOLD signal (Figure 6A). Right anterior insula showed a positive association with delivery of feedback ($z=6.68$, $p=2e-11$) and a negative association with expected values of QL1, AC2 and AC3 models ($z=[-5.4, -4.2]$, $p=[5e-12, 3e-5]$) (Figure 6B). Multicollinearity prevented differentiating among models, but BIC from meta-analytic random-effects showed that expected values from QL1 model (BIC = 309.74) showed strong evidence of better fit to BOLD signal compared to actor-critic models (AC2: BIC = 316.43; AC3: BIC = 318.36).

Orbitofrontal cortex (OFC)

Left OFC activity showed an association with general FPE of QL3 ($z=-4.38$, $p=1e-5$) (Figure 6C). No significant results were found in right OFC.

Ventromedial prefrontal cortex (vmPFC)

vmPFC showed significant negative associations with FPE of QL2 ($z=-5.39$, $p=7e-8$) and the appearance of no-winning outcome ($z=-4.46$, $p=8e-6$) (Figure 6E). These signals were collinear among them, but BIC from meta-analytic random-effects showed that the appearance of no-winning outcome (BIC = 313.64) had a better fit to BOLD signal than FPE from QL2 (BIC = 395.2).

Dorsal anterior cingulate cortex

Dorsal anterior cingulate cortex showed a negative association with the expected value of QL1 and QL3 ($z=[-4.98, -5.29]$, $p=[6e-7, 1e-7]$) (Figure 6D). Multicollinearity prevented differentiating among models and BIC from meta-analytic random-effects showed that both models showed a similar fit to BOLD signal (QL1: BIC = 332.55; QL3: BIC = 334.41).

Pre-supplementary motor area (pre-SMA)

Pre-SMA was positively associated with stimulus onset ($z=9.8$, $p=1e-22$) and negatively associated with expected values of models QL1, QL3, AC2 and AC3 ($z=[-115, -8.18]$, $p=[1e-30, 3e-16]$) (Figure 6F), but multicollinearity prevented differentiating among models. BIC from meta-analytic random-effects showed that QL1 model (BIC = 334.24) showed positive evidence of better fit than actor-critic models (AC3: BIC = 338.62; AC2: BIC = 339.35) and very strong compared to QL3 (BIC = 346.5) (Figure 6G).

Neuroimaging results for ‘group-fixed’ and ‘individual’ model fitting

In addition to the main analysis using the ‘combined fitting’ procedure, we carried out supplementary univariate regression analysis with two standard model fitting strategies, ‘group fixed’ and ‘individual’, to compare the results among model fitting methods (for detailed information of univariate results, see Table S3 for ‘individual’ and Table S4 for ‘group fixed’ in Supplementary Material). ‘Group fixed’ or ‘individual’ model fitting approaches could not reproduce the results of ‘combined fitting’ with actor-critic models in the striatum. Reward prediction error signals of actor-critic models AC2 and AC3 detected in left ventral striatum and bilateral dorsal striatum with ‘combined fitting’ were absent using ‘individual’ or ‘group fixed’ fitting approaches (Figure 7A-C). ‘Combined fitting’ also improved the fit of reward prediction error signals from AC1 to neural data, at uncorrected level, in left VS ($z=2.81$, $p_{\text{uncor}}=0.002$), left DS ($z=3.23$, $p_{\text{uncor}}=0.0006$) and right DS ($z=2.47$, $p_{\text{uncor}}=0.0067$) (Figure 7A-C). On the contrary, reward prediction error signals from QL1 and QL3 models were detected using any model fitting, but the comparison of BIC from meta-analytic random-effects model revealed that RPE signals from QL3 (but not QL1) showed a better fit to BOLD signal in left ventral and dorsal striatum when those signals were obtained using combined fitting (Figure 7D-F). In other ROIs, we found no differences in univariate regression analyses between model fitting approaches that could change the multivariate results.

Lateralization in ventral striatum

Significant prediction error signals in left and right ventral striatum showed a low correlation. Negative FPE from QL3 fitted to right VS showed a low correlation with RPE from both Q-learning (QL1: $r = 0.35$, QL3: $r = 0.35$) and actor-critic models (AC2: $r = 0.25$, AC3: $r = 0.25$) fitted to left VS. When both reward and fictive prediction error signals were introduced as predictors in the same multivariate regression model, we found no evidence of multicollinearity among them ($VIF < 2$ in all subjects). Moreover, the association between negative FPE and right VS activity remained significant when RPE signals were introduced as covariates (QL1: $z = 5.71$; QL3: $z = 5.85$; AC2: $z = 6.27$; AC3: $z = 6.18$), and the association between RPE and left VS activity remained significant when covariate by negative FPE (QL1: $z = 4.88$; QL3: $z = 4.23$; AC2: $z = 3.92$; AC3: $z = 3.86$). To quantify the asymmetry between factual and counterfactual learning signals in ventral striatum, we computed the lateralization index (LI). Fictive prediction error signals showed right dominance (QL3= -0.212 ± 0.58), and reward prediction error showed left dominance (QL1 = 0.167 ± 0.61 , QL3 = 0.172 ± 0.61 , AC2 = 0.226 ± 0.61 , AC3 = 0.175 ± 0.67). Paired samples Wilcoxon tests showed LI of fictive prediction error was significantly different than LIs of reward prediction error derived from several models (QL1: $V = 322$, $p = 0.007$, QL3: $V = 320$, $p = 0.008$, AC2: $V = 330$, $p = 0.004$, AC3: $V = 308$, $p = 0.017$).

Exploratory whole-brain analysis

Whole-brain results were consistent with ROI analyses. Right ventral striatum and ventromedial prefrontal cortex were negatively associated with negative FPE (blue regions in Figure 8), and left ventral striatum and bilateral dorsal striatum were positively associated with RPE (red-yellow regions in Figure 8). Moreover, left orbitofrontal ROI showed a partial overlap with reward prediction error activation map. Beyond the ROIs, reward prediction error signals were found in posterior cingulate and bilateral cerebellum, occipital, inferior temporooccipital, inferior parietal and dorsolateral prefrontal cortex.

Negative fictive prediction error signals were negatively associated with precuneus and midline prefrontal regions (Figure 8).

DISCUSSION

In this study we present a method ('combined fitting') to generate fMRI regressors using both behavioral and neuroimaging data. The main novelty is the introduction of a penalization term in the likelihood function that avoids subject-specific model parameters to move away from group median. The degree of penalization, e.g., the value of the penalization parameter, is decided using the fit to BOLD signal as objective function to maximize. Hence, model parameters could deviate from group median only if this deviation leads to an increase in model fit to BOLD signal. Otherwise, the penalty brings the model parameters close to the group median.

In comparison with standard model fitting, combined fitting improved the prediction of both behavioral and neural data, but only for the standard actor-critic model. Q-learning models predicted very well subjects' behavior with standard model fitting, and combined fitting did not improve those predictions, probably because of a ceiling effect (Figure 4). Moreover, parameter estimates of Q-learning did not change drastically depending on model fitting approach (Tables 1-2). On the contrary, model predictions of actor-critic failed to reproduce subject's behavior with standard fitting. Although actor-critic models also predicted a learning curve, it was below (AC1) or above (AC2 and AC3) the current subject's behavior (Figure 4A). With 'combined fitting', standard actor-critic (AC1) was able to predict the actual behavior of subjects, although extended actor-critic models (AC2 and AC3) produced even more overestimated predictions (Figure 4B-D). Combined fitting increased the value of parameter estimates, particularly for those with small values in standard fitting, e.g. alpha critic of AC1 model. Interestingly, parameters that changed the most were also those that showed a relatively better parameter recovery (Figure S9), suggesting that fit improvement was not due to poor parameter recovery of actor-critic models.

At neural level, we compared combined fitting with the standard model fitting strategies to generate fMRI regressors, 'individual' and 'group fixed' approaches (Chase et al. 2015). All methods were able to capture action-value prediction error signals derived from Q-learning models (see below for a detailed discussion about each region). Nevertheless, only 'combined fitting' allowed capturing prediction error signals derived from actor-critic models in ventral and dorsal striatum (Figure 7). All actor-critic models improved their fit to neural data with 'combined fitting', but only standard actor-critic also improved behavior predictions. Note that the introduction of neuroimaging data into model fitting avoided any circularity problem by means of a cross-validation scheme. The subjects with whom the penalization parameter was estimated were not the same as those in which that parameter was applied to perform the statistical inference. Hence, the unique ability of 'combined fitting' to capture actor-critic learning signals suggests that state-value prediction error signals are more heterogeneous across subjects during the execution of an instrumental learning task, while action-value prediction error signals are more homogeneous across subjects, more reliable across model fitting procedures and more stable across parameter estimates. Interestingly, model comparison showed that Q-learning models overcame actor-critic models at both group and individual level (Figure 4E-F), suggesting that combined fitting only improved goodness of fit of those models with a poor fit to the behavior, e.g., actor-critic models.

Prediction error signals

We replicated the presence of reward prediction error signals in left ventral striatum and bilateral dorsal striatum (O'Doherty et al., 2004; Pessiglione et al., 2006; Schonberg et al., 2007, Garrison et al., 2013; Chase et al., 2015). Interestingly, these signals were derived from both Q-learning and actor-critic models, in agreement with (Colas et al. 2017), who reported both action-value and state-value prediction error signals in ventral and dorsal striatum. However, we could not discriminate among them because of multicollinearity. On the contrary, right ventral striatum showed significant fictive prediction error but not reward prediction error signals, in agreement with previous reports of fictive learning signals in right, but not left, ventral striatum (Büchel et al. 2011; Li and Daw 2011; Tobia et al. 2014, 2016). In our study, fictive

prediction error was significant only for negative values, e.g., when counterfactual outcome was zero. Hence, our result could be interpreted as a positive association between BOLD signal and the expected value of the unchosen action, i.e. the amount of fictive loss (Büchel et al. 2011; Tobia et al. 2014). Whole-brain results showed that these results were not driven by ROIs position (Figure 8B), and laterality index confirmed the functional asymmetry in ventral striatum. Previous studies reported hemispheric asymmetries in ventral striatum during reward processing (Aberg et al. 2015) and resting-state functional connectivity (Zhang et al. 2017), although, to our knowledge, this is the first report of hemispheric asymmetry between factual and counterfactual processing in ventral striatum. Note that this finding was independent from the model fitting approach, since it was mainly driven by Q-learning signals.

To assess the influence of counterfactual processing, the comparison of interest was between standard models (AC1 and QL1) and their extended versions with the same number of parameters (AC2 and QL2). In this way, we could be sure that any improvement was driven by model complexity. At group level, actor-critic improved with counterfactual processing, but not Q-learning (Table 3). However, random-effects Bayesian model selection showed that a subset of the sample, one third of the subjects, showed QL2 as the best model (Figure 4E-F). In contrast with other studies (Palminteri et al. 2015, 2017), no explicit information about counterfactual outcome was provided during the task, making counterfactual processing rely on the knowledge about task structure that subjects learned during training by explicit instruction, i.e. when the chosen action is rewarded, the unchosen is not, and vice versa. Despite this, the inclusion of counterfactual processing improved model fit, suggesting that it is present even in the absence of counterfactual information.

Neuroimaging results also supported the role of counterfactual processing. State-value (factual) prediction error signals in the striatum were only detected when the actor-critic models included counterfactual information processing. Moreover, some cortical regions showed fictive prediction error signals derived from extended model QL3. Left anterior insula showed an association with negative fictive prediction error, in line with those studies that found fictive learning signals there, such as the prediction risk given counterfactual information (Büchel et al. 2011) or the modulatory effect of cognitive strategies on fictive error signals (Gu et al. 2014). Left orbitofrontal cortex showed a negative modulation of fictive prediction error: the higher the fictive prediction error, the lower the BOLD signal. Orbitofrontal cortex has been previously reported to be involved in counterfactual processing in patients with lesion (Camille et al. 2004) and neuroimaging studies in humans (Coricelli et al. 2005; Tobia et al. 2014), and in animal research with monkeys (Abe and Lee 2011). These results support the notion that a learning system based on factual reward prediction error is implemented subcortically, while a counterfactual learning system based on fictive prediction error is implemented both cortically and subcortically.

Value signals

Outcome delivery was significant in bilateral anterior insula, ventral and dorsal striatum. The representation of outcome value, i.e., reward delivery, was significant in both orbitofrontal and ventromedial prefrontal cortex, but only left ventromedial prefrontal cortex survived the multiple regression analysis, with a negative association with no-winning outcome. These value signals agree with recent meta-analyses of value signals in fMRI studies in humans (Bartra et al. 2013; Clithero and Rangel 2013). Furthermore, several regions signaled the expected value estimated by computational models. Pre-supplementary motor area, bilateral anterior insula, dorsal anterior cingulate cortex and right dorsal striatum showed a negative association with the expected value: the lower the expected value of the chosen action, the higher the BOLD signal. These signals were derived from Q-learning and actor-critic models. Although multicollinearity prevented us from differentiating between models, we observed that QL1 showed a better fit to BOLD signal in all ROIs. Moreover, multiple regression analyses showed that the majority of value signals remained significant after adding the other significant signals, such as stimulus onset on pre-supplementary motor area or feedback delivery on anterior insula.

Anterior insula and dorsal anterior cingulate cortex are core regions of the salience network, which is involved, among other functions, in the detection of salient events involved in reward and motivation (Menon 2015). Moreover, both regions have been associated to the cost of cognitive effort during decision-

making (Prevost et al. 2010; Shenhav et al. 2013). Our findings could be explained in terms of the increased difficulty, or cognitive effort, when deciding between actions with similar expected values, something that used to happen with lower expected values for the chosen action. To confirm this hypothesis, we performed a supplementary regression analysis between the absolute difference of the expected values of competing actions and the BOLD signal of the aforementioned regions that signaled the expected value of the chosen action. The negative association remained significant in all ROIs (Table S5 in Supplementary Material), suggesting that the activity of these regions increased when the decision was more difficult or required greater cognitive effort. This result agrees with Shenhav *et al.* (2013), who found that dACC BOLD signal was negatively associated with the value difference between competing actions. We extended this finding to bilateral insula and presupplementary motor area. The latter deserves further explanation as this negative association seems to contradict previous findings regarding its positive associations with model-free action value signals (Wunderlich et al. 2009; Wan Lee et al. 2014). Our result might be due to the anatomical closeness between ROIs in pre-SMA and dACC, suggesting that cognitive effort signaling may not be limited to the dACC but to the salience network, including the most anterior portion of pre-SMA. Moreover, pre-SMA also signaled the appearance of stimuli, consistent with its known motor preparatory function in complex processes such as learning (Ruan et al. 2018). This positive association with stimuli appearance could explain why expected value signals in pre-SMA reached the highest evidence of the study. The positive association with stimulus onset may have amplified the posterior negative association with the expected value, which is modelled at response onset, because of the post-stimulus undershoot of the hemodynamic response function.

Limitations

First, the anticorrelated nature of reward contingencies were made explicit during training, allowing the implicit inference of counterfactual outcome throughout the task. However, it made QL2 model indistinguishable from a model that updates only the value of chosen stimulus and uses it to infer the value of unchosen, i.e., $V_{\text{unchosen}} = 1 - V_{\text{chosen}}$, making fictive prediction error unnecessary. Moreover, it limited our ability to assess the contribution of different models depending on the dynamics of reward structure. Future studies using non anticorrelated reward contingencies, or in which reward structure changed over time and had to be learned throughout the task, could explore these possibilities. Second, we limited the space of penalization parameter to five values for computation time reasons. Future studies should explore either wider space or the inclusion of penalization parameter within the maximum likelihood estimation. In the latter, since the objective function would be different between the penalization parameter (fit to neural data) and the remaining parameters of the model (fit to behavioral data), it would require to decide or estimate a constrain function that weights behavioral and neural data in case of divergence (Turner et al. 2013). Third, the cross-validation scheme allowed us to prevent overfitting and circularity issues. Nevertheless, between-subjects structure of cross-validation limited the interpretability of the penalization parameter at subject level. Note that, for each fold, penalization parameter was estimated in nine tenths of the sample and applied to the remaining subjects. Hence, the penalization parameter applied to each subject was not related to his/her individual performance or underlying computations, but rather to the group average. Within-subjects cross-validation could provide penalization parameters interpretable at subject level, allowing the assessment of interindividual variability in decision-making brain computations.

Conclusions

In summary, Q-learning outperformed actor-critic at both behavioral and neural level, although the inclusion of neuroimaging data into model fitting improved the fit of actor-critic models. We observed both action-value and statevalue prediction error signals in the striatum, while standard model fitting approaches failed to capture state-value signals. The use of neuroimaging data for deciding when a subject-specific model parameter deviates too far from group median makes this method a good candidate to study clinical populations with poorer fit to behavior (Culbreth et al. 2016) or abnormal imbalance between learning systems (Gold 2012; Hernaus et al. 2019). Furthermore, we observed that both models improved their fit when included counterfactual processing. Finally, ventral striatum showed a hemispheric functional

asymmetry, with left VS signaling factual reward prediction error and right VS signaling counterfactual fictive prediction error.

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Conflicts of interest/Competing interests

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Ethics approval

The Research Ethics Committee of FIDMAG approved all study procedures, which adhered to the Declaration of Helsinki.

Consent to participate

All participants gave written informed consent prior to participation.

Consent for publication

All participants gave written informed consent prior to participation.

Availability of data and material (data transparency)

Data is available under request.

Code availability (software application or custom code)

Code is available in <https://github.com/asantoangles/rpe>

Authors' contributions

PFC, EPC and PJM developed experimental task design (designed research), ASA, PFC and IA recruited subjects and performed clinic and neuropsychological assessment (performed research), MGR, CAP and JM acquired MRI data (performed research), JM performed radiological assessment of images (performed research), ASA and JR developed model fitting procedure (contributed unpublished analytic tools), ASA and JR analyzed data, ASA and JR wrote the paper, PFC and JR reviewed the manuscript. All authors discussed the results and contributed to the final manuscript.

Figure 1. Reinforcement learning task design. In reward condition, one stimulus led to the winning outcome (the coin) in 80% of trials, whereas the other stimulus led to the winning outcome in only 20% of trials. In bivalent condition, both stimuli led to the winning outcome in 50% of trials.

Figure 2. Model fitting based on behaviour and neural responses. A) A penalization term was added to the standard model fitting based on behavioural data. The hidden variables of each model (e.g. reward prediction error of Q-learning) were convolved to the hemodynamic response function (HRF) to get the expected BOLD signal. B) The empirical BOLD signal time-course of each ROI was extracted from the pre-processed functional data. C) A cross-validation approach was used to estimate the penalization parameter that provided the highest correlation between empirical and expected BOLD signal. D) The pooled correlations (using a meta-analytic random-effects model) between the empirical BOLD signal and the cross-validation derived expected BOLD signal for each variable and model within each ROI (univariate results) were corrected for multiple comparisons using the Holm method. Within each ROI, a multicollinearity and multiple regression analysis was carried out to select variable(s) and model(s) with the best fit to the BOLD signal. α , rate of learning; α_{median} , median α of the sample; β , the (inverse) temperature; $EV_{A,t}$, expected value of A (the chosen stimulus) at time t ; $EV_{A,t+1}$, expected value of A at time $t+1$ (i.e., the following trial); HRF, hemodynamic response function; λ , penalizing parameter; $\lambda_{c,t}$, penalizing parameter for c ; $p_{c,t}$, likelihood or probability of the individual to choose the chosen stimulus at time t ; RPE_t , reward prediction error at time t ; R_t , reward at time t .

Figure 3. Percentage of optimal choices as a function of stimuli presentation. Reward condition indicates the pair of stimuli with 80:20 probability of reward for each stimulus. In bivalent condition, contingencies were 50:50. Optimal choices were defined as the selection of the stimulus with a reward contingency of 80% in reward condition, and one arbitrarily chosen stimulus in bivalent condition. The percentage of optimal choices was averaged across subjects and conditions, showing on the x-axis the number of consecutive presentations of the same pair of stimuli. Vertical lines show standard errors.

Figure 4. Learning curves in reward condition for empirical and simulated data obtained from individual model fitting (panel A), and combined fitting using neuroimaging data from left Ventral Striatum (panel B), left Dorsal Striatum (panel C) and right Dorsal Striatum (panel D). In order to show the learning process, the optimal choice was defined as the most rewarded stimulus, i.e., the stimulus with 80% of reward contingencies, independently from the actual reward in each trial. Random-effects Bayesian Model Selection using AIC (panel E) and BIC (panel F) as an approximation to log model evidence. For each subject (vertical axis), the colour code shows the posterior probability of each model (horizontal axis).

Figure 5. Multivariate results with 'combined fitting' in ventral and dorsal striatum. Plots with vertical bars (A, C, E and G) shows the significant variables and events (x-axis) and their fit to BOLD signal measured with z-value resulted from the group meta-analytic random-effects model (y-axis). Negative values in y-axis indicates a negative association. Orange lines show the 95% confidence interval. Within each ROI, collinear signals from different models were shown as grouped bars. Plots with horizontal bars (B, D, F and H) shows the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) from the group metaanalytic random-effects model. Note that the smallest BIC represents the model with better fit to BOLD signal. EV, expected value; Event, events of the task; Feedback, appearance of unsigned outcome; - FPE, negative fictive prediction error; RPE, reward prediction error; + RPE, positive reward prediction error; AC1, standard actor-critic models; AC2, extended actor-critic model with $\alpha_{actor/no-chosen} = \alpha_{actor-chosen}$; AC3, extended actor-critic model with $\alpha_{actor/no-chosen} \neq \alpha_{actor-chosen}$; QL1, standard Q-learning model; QL2, extended Q-learning model with $\alpha_{no-chosen} = \alpha_{chosen}$; QL3, extended Q-learning model with $\alpha_{no-chosen} \neq \alpha_{chosen}$.

Figure 6. Multivariate results with 'combined fitting' in anterior insula (A and B), left orbitofrontal cortex (C), dorsal anterior cingulate cortex (D), ventromedial prefrontal cortex (E), and presupplementary motor area (F). In plots with vertical bars, on the x-axis we showed variables and events significantly associated with ROIs BOLD signal; on the y-axis we showed their fit to BOLD signal measured with z-value resulted from the group meta-analytic random-effects model (y-axis). Negative values in y-axis indicates a negative correlation. Orange lines show the 95% confidence interval. Within each ROI, collinear signals from different models were shown as grouped bars. Plot with horizontal bars (panel G) shows the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) from the group meta-analytic random-effects model from the expected value in pre-Supplementary Motor Area. Note that the smallest BIC represents the model with better fit to BOLD signal. * In right anterior insula (panel B) and dorsal anterior cingulate (panel D), the difference in BIC between models was smaller than 2, making these signals indistinguishable. Abs RPE, absolute value of reward prediction error; AC1, standard actor-critic model; AC2, extended actor-critic model with $\alpha_{actor\ no-chosen} = \alpha_{actor\ chosen}$; AC3, extended actor-critic model with $\alpha_{actor\ no-chosen} \neq \alpha_{actor\ chosen}$; EV, expected value; Event, events of the task;

Feedback, appearance of unsigned outcome; - FPE, negative fictive prediction error; FPE, fictive prediction error; No-win feed, appearance of no-winning feedback; QL1, standard Q-learning model; QL2, extended Q-learning model with $\alpha_{no-chosen} = \alpha_{chosen}$; QL3, extended Q-learning model with $\alpha_{no-chosen} \neq \alpha_{chosen}$; RPE, reward prediction error; + RPE, positive reward prediction error; - RPE, negative reward prediction error; Stimulus, appearance of stimuli.

Figure 7. Comparison of model fitting approaches. Left figures (A, B and C panels) show the comparison of univariate results of reward prediction error in left ventral striatum (A), left dorsal striatum (B) and right dorsal striatum (C) using different model fitting strategies to generate the fMRI regressors: 'Combined' model fitting made use of neuroimaging data to fit the individual parameter estimates, 'Individual' fitting used the subject-specific free parameter obtained from maximum likelihood estimation, and 'Group fixed' used the median of individual parameter estimates. Red dashed lines show the threshold of significance after correction for multiple comparisons. Black dashed lines show the threshold of uncorrected significance at $p = 0.01$. Y-axis shows fit of reward prediction error to BOLD signal measured with z-value of group meta-analytic random-effects model. Right figures (D, E and F panels) show the fit of reward prediction error from QL3 to BOLD signal in left ventral striatum (D), left (E) and right (F) dorsal striatum. X-axis show the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) from meta-analytic random-effects model. Note that the smallest BIC represents the model fitting approach with better fit to BOLD signal. AC2, extended actor-critic model with $\alpha_{actor, no-chosen} = \alpha_{actor, chosen}$; AC3, extended actor-critic model with $\alpha_{actor, no-chosen} \neq \alpha_{actor, chosen}$; QL1, standard Q-learning model; QL3, extended Q-learning model with $\alpha_{no-chosen} \neq \alpha_{chosen}$.

Figure 8. Exploratory whole-brain analysis. Yellow-red shows regions signalling reward prediction error of standard Q-learning model (QL1) fitted to left ventral striatum, and blue shows brain regions signalling negative fictive prediction error of extended QL3 model fitted to right ventral striatum. Green dots indicate regions-of-interest (panel A) and black lines shows bilateral ventral striatum from Harvard-Oxford anatomical atlas (panel B). Both panels show the same statistical maps, but a mask of striatum was used in panel B for display purposes. Left hemisphere is shown in the left side.

		Q-learning			Actor-critic		
		Standard	Extended		Standard	Extended	
		(QL1)	$\alpha_{nc}=\alpha$ (QL2)	$\alpha_{nc}\neq\alpha$ (QL3)	(AC1)	$\alpha_{actor,nc}=\alpha_{actor}$ (AC2)	$\alpha_{actor,nc}\neq\alpha_{actor}$ (AC3)
α	α_{critic}	0.42 ± 0.22	0.032 ± 0.18	0.28 ± 0.21	0.004 ± 0.12	0.22 ± 0.24	0.001 ± 0.27
	α_{actor}				0.99 ± 0.42	0.49 ± 0.19	0.49 ± 0.32
α_{nc}	$\alpha_{actor,nc}$	---	---	0.02 ± 0.20	---	---	0.30 ± 0.35
B		0.22 ± 0.17	0.05 ± 0.21	0.20 ± 0.21	0.48 ± 1.01	0.44 ± 0.39	0.38 ± 0.15

Table 1. Parameter estimates of the standard model fitting based on behavioral data. Median and standard deviation of parameter estimates of Q-learning and actor-critic models. α , rate of learning; α_{critic} , rate of learning of the critic; α_{actor} , rate of learning of the actor; α_{nc} , counterfactual rate of learning; $\alpha_{actor,nc}$, counterfactual rate of learning of the actor; β , (inverse) temperature.

		Q-learning			Actor-critic		
		Standard	Extended		Standard	Extended	
		(QL1)	$\alpha_{nc}=\alpha$ (QL2)	$\alpha_{nc}\neq\alpha$ (QL3)	(AC1)	$\alpha_{actor,nc}=\alpha_{actor}$ (AC2)	$\alpha_{actor,nc}\neq\alpha_{actor}$ (AC3)
α	α_{critic}	0.43 ± 0.17	0.041 ± 0.13	0.34 ± 0.18	0.02 ± 0.02	0.32 ± 0.12	0.36 ± 0.14
	α_{actor}				0.99 ± 2e-4	0.51 ± 0.16	0.61 ± 0.15
α_{nc}	$\alpha_{actor,nc}$	---	---	0.016 ± 0.043	---	---	0.59 ± 0.19
B		0.225 ± 0.15	0.083 ± 0.12	0.21 ± 0.16	0.5 ± 0.24	0.48 ± 0.21	0.44 ± 0.21

Table 2. Parameter estimates of the model fitting based on behavioural and neuroimaging data ('combined fitting'), averaged across subjects and ROIs. Median and standard deviation are shown. α , rate of learning; α_{critic} , rate of learning of the critic; α_{actor} , rate of learning of the actor; α_{nc} , counterfactual rate of learning; $\alpha_{actor,nc}$, counterfactual rate of learning of the actor; β , (inverse) temperature.

	LLH	AIC	BIC
Standard Q-learning - QL1	-30.68 (10.1)	65.36 (20.42)	71.51 (20.42)
Extended Q-learning ($\alpha_{nc}=\alpha$) - QL2	-33.77 (9.95)	71.55 (19.9)	77.7 (19.9)
Extended Q-learning ($\alpha_{nc}\neq\alpha$) - QL3	-29.29 (10.3)	64.58 (20.6)	73.80 (20.6)
Standard actor-critic - AC1	-41.69 (15.44)	89.38 (30.89)	98.61 (30.89)
Extended actor-critic ($\alpha_{actor,nc}=\alpha_{actor}$) - AC2	-38.06 (9.95)	82.12 (19.9)	91.35 (19.89)
Extended actor-critic ($\alpha_{actor,nc}\neq\alpha_{actor}$) - AC3	-34.74 (9.49)	77.48 (18.99)	89.78 (18.99)

Table 3. Classic model selection criteria based on standard model fitting based on behavioural data. Mean (sd) across subjects. AIC, Akaike Information Criteria; BIC, Bayesian Information Criterion; LLH, log likelihood. Higher values of LLH, and lower values of AIC and BIC indicates better fit of the model to behavioural data. Note that we did not use AIC or BIC to compare models directly, but rather as inputs for a random-effects Bayesian Model Selection.